

Triplet-Triplet Annihilation Upconversion by Polymeric Sensitizers

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ABSTRACT

Triplet-triplet annihilation up-conversion (TTAUC) is an emerging technology in photonics with significant potential to impact a variety of fields (e.g. solar cells, bioimaging, drug delivery) due to its ability to convert long-wavelength photons to higher photon energies even at low excitation power densities. However, for many practical applications of TTAUC, the transfer of the upconversion system, consisting of a molecular sensitizer and a molecular annihilator, from solution, in which efficient TTAUC systems have been reported, to solid matrices is required. This is a challenge because diffusion facilitates the close contact between molecular components required for TTET and TTA. To this end, various approaches to fully integrate sensitizer and annihilator into polymers or combining a macromolecular annihilator with monomeric sensitizers have been established. This contribution studies the effect of integrating Ru(dqp)₂-inspired molecular sensitizers into the side chains of a PMMA polymer, which – as macromolecular photosensitizer – is co-dissolved with 9,10-diphenylanthracene as annihilator. We study the effect of confining the sensitizers into a comparably small volume on the TTAUC process and compare the results to an upconversion system using various concentrations of monomeric annihilator. We show that our approach of using a macromolecular photosensitizer allows for upconversion at extremely low excitation power densities. Furthermore, the onset of the strong annihilation regime, i.e. the regime in which the intensity of the upconverted light scales linearly with the increase of the excitation power, is significantly reduced using the polymeric sensitizer; however, the upconversion intensity sits below the monomeric counterparts.

INTRODUCTION

Triplet-triplet annihilation upconversion (TTAUC) has recently drawn a lot of interest as it allows for photon upconversion (green to blue,¹ red to green,² red to yellow,³ NIR to blue,⁴) at low power density using non-coherent light. Introduced by Parker and Hatchard in 1962,⁵ TTAUC (Figure 1A) is a diffusion-controlled bimolecular process, in which a sensitizer (S) absorbs low-energy photons. Upon excitation to the first singlet excited state (¹S), the sensitizer undergoes intersystem crossing (ISC) to reach its first triplet excited state (³S). The collision with an annihilator (A) enables triplet-triplet energy transfer (TTET) to populate the annihilator's triplet state (³A). Two of such annihilator triplet states (³A) annihilate in mutual collision (triplet-triplet annihilation, TTA) yielding one highly excited annihilator singlet emissive state (¹A). The energy of this state is higher than the energy of the ¹S state. If ¹A decays radiatively, a photon is emitted, which is blue-shifted compared to the excitation light. In solution TTET and TTA are diffusion-controlled processes and depend, e.g., on the viscosity of the medium. Thus, TTAUC is most efficient in liquids which allow for fast diffusion of sensitizer and annihilator.

TTAUC has been applied to increase light harvesting in solar cells,⁶⁻⁹ to activate photocatalytic transformations with low-intensity near-IR light⁴ and has found applications in biosensing,¹⁰ bioimaging,^{11,12} polymerization,¹³ organic light emitting diode¹⁴ and light-activated drug release.¹⁵⁻¹⁸ Despite its potential, it still remains challenging to implement practical applications of TTAUC. Most TTAUC systems require inert conditions to function, in particular the exclusion of oxygen is essential because the triplet excited states, which are key to the molecular mechanism of TTAUC, are easily quenched by molecular oxygen. Thus, deoxygenation is key for efficient TTET to take place. Hence, the TTAUC systems still require substantial optimization to transfer successful concepts functioning well in solution to materials. For instance, TTAUC systems have been realized in solid state/gel environment and fully polymer integrated systems.¹⁹⁻²⁰ Different strategies to chemically link sensitizers and annihilator to an optically inert polymer were developed, such polymer remains inert to excitation or emission photon. Islangulov et al. used an ethylene oxide-epichlorohydrin copolymer P(EO-EP) as a rubbery host to link sensitizer and annihilator.²¹⁻²³ The low crystallinity and glass transition temperature allow the linked molecules to diffuse and participate in TTET and TTA.²¹ Durandin et al. incorporated sensitizer and annihilator into poly(ethylene glycol),¹⁹ which was doped with oleic acid (PEG-OA)²⁴ to overcome the O₂ quenching of triplet states.^{25,26} Sittig et al. covalently integrated the sensitizer and annihilator to poly(methacrylate)s to achieve upconversion in a novel metal free, all-polymer system.⁵ Furthermore, Lee et al. mechanistically studied the interaction of monomeric sensitizers with methacrylate and methylmethacrylate (MMA)-bound annihilators in glassy material, the upconversion was observed at low power density 32 mWcm⁻².²⁷

While polymer or gel integration of the molecular sensitizers and annihilators have been successful towards upconversion in solid-state systems, also other approaches have been reported towards this goal: halide perovskite or colloidal nanocrystals as sensitizer and DBP (tetraphenyldibenzoperiflanthene) doped rubrene as annihilator have been utilized to enhance the efficiency of solar cells. For instance, Bawendi and coworkers used submonolayer PbS nanocrystals as sensitizer and rubrene (DBP doped) as annihilator in solar cells, which showed threshold density (I_{th} , described later in the manuscript) of 12 W cm⁻² and efficiency near 7% of absorbed photons into higher- energy emissive states for excitation at 808 nm.²⁸ Nienhaus et al. used methylammonium formamidinium lead triiodide (MAFA) of different thickness for sensitization of rubrene (DBP doped) triplets, MAFA film of thickness 380 nm resulted in threshold density of 7.1 mW cm⁻².²⁹ MacQueen et al. demonstrated 500nm thick

methylammonium lead iodide (MAPI) perovskite and rubrene (DBP doped) as an annihilator in a bilayer system, which showed efficient TTA but the overall efficiency was low.³⁰

To date, in the majority of reported systems copolymerization of both sensitizer and annihilator or embedding of both components into a polymer matrix or gel are the used approaches.^{19–27} However, the effect of confining only the sensitizer into a macromolecule, which is co-dissolved with monomeric annihilators, on the TTAUC process has not yet been explored to the best of our knowledge. Notably, such an approach has proved beneficial in the context of, e.g., photochemical sensitization of singlet oxygen ($^1\text{O}_2$).²⁸ Liu and coworkers polymerized a sensitizer for $^1\text{O}_2$ generation and reported increased $^1\text{O}_2$ yields.³¹ As TTET is a key process for the activation of $^1\text{O}_2$, we speculate that the approach of exploiting polymeric sensitizers might also benefit TTAUC systems.

Various Ruthenium-polypyridyl-type complexes and 9,10-diphenylanthracene (DPA) constitute well known pair of sensitizer and annihilator, respectively. Both species have been studied with respect to their applicability in triplet-triplet energy transfer (TTET):^{20,32} For example, Boutin et al. demonstrated TTAUC in polymer-linked $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{2+}$ (bpy is 2,2-bipyridine) and DPA as sensitizer and annihilator, respectively.²⁰ Several other reports describe Ruthenium-based sensitizer and DPA as annihilators.^{33–36} In the present work, to investigate TTAUC in a system comprising a polymer bound sensitizer and mobile annihilator we exploit the ester-decorated $[\text{Ru}(\text{dqp})_2]^{2+}$ complex (dqp is 2,6-di(quinolin-8-yl)pyridine) as monomeric triplet sensitizer (MS). The $[\text{Ru}(\text{dqp})_2]^{2+}$ complex benefits with respect to the bpy-based congeners from prolonged excited state lifetimes in the microsecond timescale.³⁷ This sensitizer is well suited for the energy transfer (TTET) to donors like DPA.^{38–40} The Ru-PMMA copolymer functions as polymeric triplet sensitizer (PS), in which the $[\text{Ru}(\text{dqp})_2]^{2+}$ units are covalently linked to poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) backbone,⁴¹ while DPA serves as an unbound molecular annihilator in TTAUC.

Figure 1: (A) TTAUC mechanism- green upward arrow depicts the absorption of sensitizer, red downward arrow shows emission of sensitizer, two dashed downward arrows from $^3S^*$ and $^3A^*$ represent undesired decay of excited triplet sensitizer and annihilator respectively, blue downward arrow represents delayed fluorescence (upconversion). (B) Absorption and emission spectra of molecules under investigation, excitation wavelength is 532 nm for **MS** and **PS**, 355 nm for DPA. Chemical structure of (C) **MS**(D) **PS** (E) DPA

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Samples. All experiments have been conducted in deaerated acetonitrile (ACN). Deaeration is carried out using freeze pump thaw. The samples are carried in 1 cm Schlenk-cuvettes to maintain inert condition for all steady-state and time-resolved measurements. The sensitizer concentration is kept constant 5 μM and three concentrations of annihilator 10 μM , 50 μM , 250 μM are used for upconversion and quenching experiments. The following sample nomenclature is adopted throughout the article: monomeric sensitizers (**MS**) of 10 μM concentration mixed with 20 μM of DPA in deaerated acetonitrile results in a sample containing 5 μM of **MS** and 10 μM of DPA, which is referred to as **M-10**; likewise, other samples were prepared with different concentration of DPA keeping sensitizer concentration constant, see the below table for details.

Table 1. Concentration and nomenclature of the investigated samples.

Constituents of the sample	Sensitizer concentration (μM)	Annihilator concentration (μM)	Nomenclature
MS and DPA	5	10	M-10
	5	50	M-50
	5	250	M-250
PS and DPA	5	10	P-10
	5	50	P-50
	5	250	P-250

Steady state spectroscopy. Absorption spectra are recorded using a Jasco V780 UV/Vis/NIR spectrophotometer. Excitation spectra are recorded using a FLS980 emission spectrophotometer (Edinburgh Instruments) with a Xenon lamp as excitation source (ozone free 450W). The excitation wavelength for all emission measurement is 532 nm (CW532-100, Roithner LaserTechnik GmbH). The absolute quantum yield of emission, Φ , of **MS** is determined using an integrated sphere. Φ of **PS** and the upconversion yields, Φ_{UC} , are determined relative to the quantum yield determined of **MS**, Φ_{MS} . Maximum theoretical efficiency of the upconversion emission quantum yield is considered to be 50%.⁴²

Time resolved spectroscopy. Nanosecond time-resolved absorption and emission data have been measured using a custom-built setup reported earlier.²⁰ In brief, a Nd:YAG laser generates 5 ns pulses at a repetition rate of 10 Hz to pump an OPO, which generates the excitation wavelengths in the visible range. A 75W Xenon arc lamp provides the probe light. A five-stage Hamamatsu R928 photomultiplier (PMT) is placed at the exit slit of monochromator to detect the probe beam. The electronics to process the transient signal is developed by Pascher Instruments (Lund, Sweden).

In the experiments reported here, we chose 532 nm as excitation wavelength. A notch filter at 532 nm (Edmund optics) is used to block pump scatter from entering the detector. The pump pulse energy is adjusted to 0.10 ± 0.01 mJ. Lifetime of the species is determined by global fit of nanosecond time-resolved absorption measurements. Fitting routine in Origin 2019 is used to global fit the spectra and the decay associated with the spectra is used to assign the lifetimes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Steady state absorption and emission spectroscopy. Figure 1 displays the absorption and emission spectra of **MS**, **PS** and DPA. **MS** shows the typical absorption features of a $[\text{Ru}(\text{dqp})_2]^{2+}$ -type complex as reported in literature.^{20,39,43,44} The chromophore concentration of **PS** is chosen in such a way that the optical density remains the same for **MS** and **PS** at 532 nm. While the absorption spectra of **PS** and **MS** are overall very similar, a slight shift in the absorption spectra of **PS** near 450 and 550 nm with respect to **MS** is observed. The occurrence of a bathochromic shoulder has been reported earlier and can be attributed to the electronic effects of the substituent, i.e., the electron-withdrawing ester moiety vs. slightly electron-donating alkyl group.³⁹ The emission spectra of **MS** and **PS** in the range between 600 and 800 nm are virtually identical and resemble the typical shape of the ³MLCT phosphorescence of $[\text{Ru}(\text{dqp})_2]^{2+}$ -type complexes. DPA absorbs in the range between 350 and 415 nm. Its emission is observed between 375 and 525 nm. Upconversion is observed in all six samples mentioned earlier: When exciting the sample at 532 nm, the typical DPA emission at below 500 nm is evident (Figure 2A).^{9,45}

Figure 2: (A) Upconversion emission of **M-10**, **M-50**, **M-250**, **P-10**, **P-50** and **P-250**; all spectra are measured with an excitation density of $850 mW cm^{-2}$ and are normalized at the emission maximum of **M-250** at 427 nm. (B) Power density vs. upconversion quantum yield, $\Phi_{MS} = 3.6\%$, $\Phi_{PS} = 0.7\%$; (C) & (D) log (Power density) vs. log (Integrated upconversion emission intensity), $R^2(COD) \approx 0.98$ in all fitting case; for **P-250** low annihilation regime slope is 1.8 and high annihilation regime slope is 1.2 which is considered as 2 and 1 respectively in Figure (D).

The effect of increasing the concentration of DPA on upconversion can be seen in Figure 2; for instance, the peak of the normalized emission intensity at 427 nm (Figure 2A) increases with increasing DPA concentration. The integrated area under the upconverted emission spectra for **M-10**, **M-50** and **M-250** are 8.2, 36.3 and 54.8 respectively and for **P-10**, **P-50** and **P-250** are 0.5, 16.9 and 50.3 respectively. The comparison shows that the increase in upconversion signal upon increasing DPA is steeper when using **PS** when compared to **MS**. The absolute fluorescence quantum yield of **MS** is 3.6%; the relative quantum yield of **PS** is 0.7%.³⁹ In the following, we use the quantum yield of **MS** as reference for all relative quantum yield measurements. The upconversion emission quantum yields (Figure 2B) upon using excitation power densities of $1130 mW cm^{-2}$ for **M-10**, **M-50** and **M-250** are 0.7, 2.3 and 4.8%, for **P-10**, **P-50** and **P-250** are <0.1, 1.7 and 4.8%, respectively. Thus, also the increase of the quantum yield with increasing DPA concentration is steeper for **PS** compared to **MS**. The maximum upconversion quantum yield measured at $4900 mW cm^{-2}$ are 0.2%, 2.2% and 6.3% for **P-10**, **P-50** and **P-250** respectively; for their monomeric counterparts **M-10**, **M-50** and **M-250** upconversion quantum yields of 1.2%, 3.7% and 8.4% have been determined, respectively.

The upconversion intensity as a function of excitation power density, either considered directly (Figure 2C and 2D) or as reflected in the upconversion quantum yield (Figure 2B), increases strongly at low excitation power densities up to ca. 1000 mWcm^{-2} . This is followed by a region with a significantly reduced slope at higher excitation power densities. This inflection indicates the transition from the weak to the strong annihilation regime, as typically observed in literature.^{46–48} The threshold power density (I_{th}) at which the strong upconversion limit is reached is ca. 1444 mWcm^{-2} for **M-10** and 756 mWcm^{-2} for **M-50** and **M-250**. Thus, increasing the DPA concentration from **M-50** to **M-250** does not reduce the I_{th} further despite an increase in the absolute upconversion emission intensity. The I_{th} for **P-50** and **P-250** is 548 mWcm^{-2} and 257 mWcm^{-2} , respectively. There is no apparent turnover from a weak to a strong annihilation regime for **P-10**, indicating the inefficiency of the system in terms of upconversion. Judging the efficiency of upconversion by the threshold of the strong annihilation regime, we conclude that **P-250** is the most efficient system for TTAUC. This observation is reminiscent of the observations made by Sittig et al. on a fully polymer-integrated upconversion system,⁵ who also observed an essentially linear rise of the upconversion intensity from very low excitation power densities.

Generally, increasing the annihilator concentration leads to more collision partners in the vicinity of a given excited sensitizer. Hence, the probability of TTET increases. However, increasing the DPA concentration beyond a certain threshold can cause aggregate and excimer formation that, in turn, limit upconversion emission.^{49–51} Increasing the excitation power density makes available more photons for absorption by ground state sensitizer molecules, consequently increasing the concentration of excited ^3S sensitizers and in turn the efficiency of TTET and TTA, ultimately increasing the upconversion emission. The excitation power density, at which triplet bimolecular ($^3\text{A}-^3\text{A}$) annihilation becomes so rapid that the intrinsic decay of a given ^3A does not limit the TTA-UC kinetics, is referred to as threshold power density (I_{th}); in other words, the triplet decay pathways are minimized to the least and ($^3\text{A}-^3\text{A}$) TTA governs the upconversion rate. Beyond this intensity the upconversion intensity scales linearly with increasing excitation power density and the upconversion quantum yield appears to saturate. At this point, the weak annihilation regime converts to the strong annihilation regime yielding a maximum upconversion efficiency.^{47,48,52–54}

In the **PS** samples, the sensitizer units are covalently attached to the polymer chain, resulting in a non-homogeneous distribution of sensitizers in the sample. Within the volume occupied by the polymer chain the concentration of **PS** is high, while other regions of the sample are depleted of **PS**. Judging from the conversion of the MMA (79%) and considering the initial ratio of MMA/monomer (95/5), an average **PS** chain should contain 75 MMA units and 4 Ru centers. The NMR integration of representative protons gives the relative content of Ru units vs. MMA units of 6%, which agrees well with the observed smooth conversion and feed ratio of polymerization (Table S1). In essence, it can be safely assumed, that multiple Ru centers are embedded in a representative polymer chain. The uneven distribution of the sensitizers affects the upconverting system in the following ways: (i) TTAUC occurs only in the vicinity of the **PS**, i.e., in the vicinity of the polymer strands. (ii) Consequently, also the ^3A formed by TTET, are spatially restrained to the vicinity of the polymer strands. As a result, the ^3A are not required to diffuse far in order to encounter a second ^3A reaction partner for TTA. Thus, this scenario results in very efficient TTAUC (strong annihilation) in the vicinity of the polymers, which essentially form “upconversion hot spots”.^{55,56,57} On the other hand, sensitizers and annihilators

are homogeneously distributed in **MS** containing samples. As a result, upconversion takes place across the excitation focal volume. (iii) A large fraction of the DPA annihilators, i.e., those in the partial volumes, in which no **PS** is present, does not participate in upconversion process. The polymer backbone, which keeps the sensitizer molecules tied, can hinder the free diffusion of sensitizer molecules as well as of DPA molecules by barricading their diffusion path, which may affect the TTET and collisional TTA, ultimately limiting the upconversion emission.⁵⁸ (iv) Finally, the compartmentalization of the sensitizer in PS units reduces the upconversion by reabsorption from first excited singlet state of DPA to PS via Förster resonance energy transfer.^{40,59,60} When the excitation power density is low and only a few sensitizers are excited, the chances of back energy transfer from localized excited singlet DPA to (non-excited) **PS** within the “upconversion hot spot” are higher, due to the presence of many sensitizers, in the ground state, in the vicinity of a given excited 1A . Back-energy transfer (reabsorption) can also occur when the excitation power density is high. However, due to low number of ground state sensitizer molecules, we consider it unlikely, that the process will dominate the experimentally observed signature. As a result of the above considerations, alteration of excitation power density or DPA concentration has greater impact in **PS** containing samples. The above-mentioned explanations (i), (ii) and (iii) can be visualized in Figure (3).

The upconversion system **P-10** suffers in two ways: at low excitation power density, i.e., in the weak annihilation regime, a relatively high number of non-excited sensitizers are in the vicinity of an excited emissive 1A . Hence, a comparably large fraction of the sensitizers participates in reabsorption (see (iv), above). For high excitation power density powers, there is sufficient 3S available to (in principal) afford efficient TTA-UC. However, the overall low number of DPA molecules, that can act as energy acceptors in the TTET process in the vicinity of a given excited **P-10** sensitizer, reduces the probability of TTA taking place. Hence **P-10** apparently never reaches the strong annihilation regime. Consequently, neither its quantum yield appears to saturate (Figure 2B) nor does its upconversion intensity vs. excitation power density reaches a slope of 1 (Figure 2D).

Figure 3: Representative image of **MS** and **PS** in DPA, the TTAUC is from localized sensitizers in **PS** samples but homogeneously distributed sensitizers in **MS** samples.

NANOSECOND TIME RESOLVED SPECTROSCOPY

Nanosecond time-resolved spectroscopy was carried out to investigate the kinetics of the TTAUC process. Figure 4 summarizes the respective ns transient absorption data. The decay associated spectra resulting from the fitting of the data are displayed in the Supporting Information (see Figure S2). Figure 4A shows the stimulated emission for **MS** centered at 700 nm, a ground-state bleach (GSB) at 500 nm and excited-state absorption (ESA) near 400 nm. A mono-exponential global fit of the data reveals a characteristic decay time of 4.5 μs , which we ascribe to the triplet state lifetime of **MS**. The spectral characteristics and observed decay time are in line with previous reports by Hammarström and colleagues, who originally introduced $[\text{Ru}(\text{dqp})_2]^{2+}$.^{39,61} **PS** shows similar spectral features (Figure 4B). However, a mono-exponential global fit of the data results in a characteristic lifetime of only 2.5 μs . In addition to the shortened triplet lifetime upon polymer integration of the sensitizer, the relative band intensities change: For **PS** the stimulated emission band is less pronounced than for **MS**. The DPA of 50 μM in similar experimental conditions revealed an excited state lifetime of 3.1 ms lifetime, which is in line with literature reports.^{52,62} The transient absorption spectra of DPA are shown in supporting information (Figure S3).

Upon addition of annihilator (Figure 4C and 4D) to the sensitizer solutions, the differential absorption features of the sensitizer remain visible, however, an additional ESA band at 425 nm emerges, which is indicative of the triplet state of DPA.⁶³ In the presence of DPA, the ^3S lifetime of **MS** in **M-50** gets shortened to 2.4 μs due to TTET, while the lifetime of ^3A is 160 μs . The corresponding data for **P-50** is shown in Figure 4D and basically reveals the same spectral features. However, also for the polymeric sensitizer an additional ESA at 425 nm is

visible upon addition of the annihilator, which we attribute to the triplet state of DPA. Kinetic analysis yields lifetimes of the 3S and 3A of 2.0 μ s and 210 μ s, respectively.

Figure 4: Nanosecond transient absorption spectra (normalized) of (A) **MS**, $\tau_{MS} = 4.5\mu$ s (B) **PS**, $\tau_{PS} = 2.5\mu$ s; spectra A and B normalized by peak of GSB (C) **M-50**, $\tau_{MS} = 2.4\mu$ s, $\tau_{DPA} = 160\mu$ s (D) **P-50**, $\tau_{PS} = 2.0\mu$ s, $\tau_{DPA} = 210\mu$ s. Bottom of A and B - inverted emission in red and inverted absorbance in green. Bottom of C and D - overlap of excited state absorption of 3S in violet and 3A in blue. τ represents the triplet lifetime of the individual species as indicated in the subscript. The transient absorption spectrum of the DPA is shown in supporting information (S3).

The triplet state lifetime of the **PS** is reduced compared to the lifetime of **MS**. The higher triplet lifetime of **MS** molecules will populate more⁴⁷ triplet annihilator 3A through TTET than **PS**, which appear as higher Absorbance of 3A centering around 425nm in **M-50** (Figure 4C) than **P-50** (Figure 4D), which finally results in higher number of TTA and higher upconversion intensity.

Table 2. Triplet state lifetimes

	MS	PS	DPA	M-10	M-50	M-250	P-10	P-50	P-250
3S τ (μ s)	4.5	2.5	-	3.8	2.4	0.9	2.4	2	1
3A τ (μ s)	-	-	3100	340	160	120	>1000	210	190

Lifetimes determined from global fitting, maximum deviation is within 10% of the given value. DPA sample is 50 mM in deaerated acetonitrile and excited at 410 nm.

The lifetime of the 3A reduces slightly from 340 μs to 120 μs upon increasing the annihilator concentration in the monomeric sensitizer system. A more pronounced impact of annihilator concentration is observed for the upconversion systems relying on the polymer sensitizers. For 3A in **P-10** the triplet lifetime is larger than 1 ms, upon increasing the annihilator concentration to **P-250** the 3A drops to 190 μs . We ascribe this to the higher density of 3A in the “upconversion hot spots” in the vicinity of the **PS**, which cause TTA to be more efficient and thus shortening the lifetime of the 3A .

Figure 5A and 5B show nanosecond transient decay kinetics recorded at 380 nm (ESA), 500 nm (GSB) and 700 nm (SE) of **MS** and **PS**, respectively. An overlay of the curves indicates that ESA, GSB and SE decay with the same lifetime, and lifetimes assessed by global fitting also gives the same values, the deviation in the lifetime assessed by global fitting and mono-exponential decay fit is within 10%. Figure 5C and 5D display the transient decay kinetics recorded at 380 nm (reflecting ESA of sensitizer) and 440 nm (reflecting ESA of annihilator) of **MS** and **PS** respectively.

Figure 5: Decay transients from nanosecond transient absorption spectra recorded at 380 nm, 440 nm, 500 nm, and 700nm are shown in violet, blue, green, red respectively, line and symbol represent the raw data and dashed line represents the exponential fit. In figure (A) and (B) normalized decay transients recorded at 380 nm, 500 nm (inverted) and 700 nm (inverted) are shown, dashed line in violet represents mono-exponential decay fit to spectra at 380nm, fitting for 500nm and 700nm are not shown. τ represents the triplet lifetime of the individual species as indicated in the subscript. (A) **MS**, fits at 380 nm, 500 nm and 700 nm are τ_{MS} are 4.6 μs , 4.3 μs and 4.5 μs respectively. (B) **PS**, fits at 380 nm, 500 nm and 700 nm are $\tau_{\text{PS}} = 2.5 \mu\text{s}$, 2.5 μs , 2.6 μs respectively. (C) **M50**, $\tau_{\text{MS}} = 2.5 \mu\text{s}$ (violet), build up $\tau_{\text{DPA}} = 2.1 \mu\text{s}$, decay $\tau_{\text{DPA}} = 150 \mu\text{s}$ (blue). (D) **P50**, $\tau_{\text{PS}} = 2.0 \mu\text{s}$, build up $\tau_{\text{DPA}} =$

3.3 μs , decay $\tau_{\text{DPA}} = 230 \mu\text{s}$. Reduces Chi-square ≤ 0.003 in all fitting cases. Spectra are normalized by their respective peak. Maximum error is within 10% of the given value.

Stern-Volmer analysis based on the sensitizer triplet lifetimes in the absence (τ_0) and presence of (τ) DPA enables quantification of the triplet-triplet energy transfer rate constant, k_{TTET} . To this end, Figure 6 depicts the quenching of the ^3S by three different concentrations of annihilator. Lifetimes used in the plot is shown in Table 2.

Figure 6: Stern-Volmer constants (K_{SV}) and bimolecular triplet-triplet energy transfer rate constant (k_{TTET}) obtained using dynamic quenching Stern-Volmer equation. $R^2(\text{COD}) > 0.99$ in both the fitting cases.

Analysis of the changes in lifetime upon increasing the annihilator concentration is performed according to

$$\frac{\tau_0}{\tau} = 1 + K_{\text{SV}}[Q] = 1 + k_{\text{TTET}}\tau_0[Q] \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Where K_{SV} is the Stern-Volmer quenching constant and $[Q]$ refers to the DPA concentration.

k_{TTET} for the monomeric and polymeric system were determined as $3.6 \cdot 10^9 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ and $2.2 \cdot 10^9 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$, respectively, which is in line with reports on energy transfer between Ruthenium-complex based sensitizers to DPA.^{35,45} We attribute the higher k_{TTET} in the monomeric system to the free diffusion of the sensitizer molecules; in polymeric system, in which - on average - four Ru complexes in the sidechains of 75 MMA repeat units in the polymer backbone constitute one macromolecule **PS**. Thus, **PS** is overall much larger than a molecular sensitizer, evidently larger size will limit the diffusivity of the sensitizer resulting in decreased k_{TTET} .⁶⁴

CONCLUSIONS

The integration of molecular sensitizers or annihilators into polymers presents one approach towards solid-state up-conversion systems relying on triplet-triplet annihilation. To this end, mechanistic studies of polymer-integrated sensitizer and annihilator are essential. Thus, this paper compares the effect of polymer-integrated sensitizers to monomeric sensitizers on the up-conversion mechanism, when the sensitizers are in solution with DPA as annihilator. We chose $[\text{Ru}(\text{dqp})_2]^{2+}$ -type complexes as sensitizer, which is established as a $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{2+}$ -

inspired chromophore with an extremely long $^3\text{MLCT}$ lifetime as a prerequisite for triplet-triplet energy transfer from the sensitizer to the annihilator units. A polymeric upconversion system with low annihilator concentration (**P-10**) appears inefficient at low excitation power density. However, increasing DPA concentration and excitation power density improves the performance of the polymeric upconversion system to the extent that it matches one of its monomeric counterparts. Increasing the annihilator concentration with the polymeric sensitizer, **P-250**, yields a very efficient upconversion system. Apparently, compartmentalization of the sensitizer molecules, to produce hotspots for upconversion, immensely favors the upconversion by reducing the diffusion length and time for TTET and TTA.

The threshold power density (I_{th}), above which TTAUC occurs in the strong annihilation regime, is 257 mWcm^{-2} (**P-250**) and 756 mWcm^{-2} (**M-250**). The lower I_{th} in the polymeric upconversion systems is due to the efficient triplet-triplet annihilation in the vicinity of the individual polymer chains. The drop in the I_{th} is remarkable, as the parameter plays an important role in judging a system's potential suitability for practical application, e.g., solar radiation harvesting in solar cells. Thus, lowering I_{th} will help to TTAUC materials for solar cells of photoelectrochemical cells. Despite the much lower I_{th} in the polymeric system, overall upconversion emission intensity is higher in case of monomeric systems.

Time-resolved measurements complement the mechanistic studies in this manuscript and shows that **P-10** doesn't undergo efficient quenching of sensitizer triplet state, i.e., the inefficient TTET and the higher ^3A lifetime indicates poor TTA. However, **P-250** revealed well-quenched sensitizer triplet state (i.e. better TTET), although lower than monomeric counterpart, and very comparable ^3A lifetime to monomeric one i.e. very efficient TTA. This pronounced change in ^3S and ^3A lifetime in polymeric upconversion system from **P-10** to **P-250** is attributed to efficient upconversion at the hotspots. Thus, the work presented here suggests polymeric sensitizers to be suitable models for efficient upconversion systems, which can be useful to synthesize upconversion in solid matrices and can find further practical applications like in solar cells, bioimaging.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION DESCRIPTION

Optical characterization, decay associated spectra, synthesis-instrumentation and NMR spectra.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank Avinash Chettri and Maria Sittig for assistance in initial phase of experiments and discussions. The work was financially supported by the European Commission via the grant 813920. CSB and TEK gratefully acknowledge Science Foundation Ireland for funding under grant number [19/FFP/6428]. KKJ thanks Dr. Anja Schulz for assistance in collaboration and facilitations.

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TOC Graph

